

WHAT IS REINCARNATE

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

KEY FACTS

Demo Case / Value Chain

SLAMD / Flat glass and concrete (CDW)

Lead Partners

Ragn-Sells, BAM

Innovation(s) applied

Valuation of recycled materials

TRL (before → after)

[4 → 6]

Related Deliverables

[D1.4, D3.4, D5.2, D5.3]

CONTEXT AND INNOVATION

This study is an exploration of how SLAMD can help shorten the experimental time of developing new recipes with alternative binders from CDW (glass and concrete) for new concrete production. The expected outcomes are SLAMD could be able to suggest and predict recipes that fulfill the requirement (compressive strength).

DEMONSTRATION AND RESULTS

The Ragn-Sells / BAM demo used SLAMD to iteratively optimize mortar formulations incorporating recycled glass and concrete fines. The objective was to achieve a cement replacement rate of at least 30% while maintaining a minimum 28-day compressive strength (fc28d) of 30 MPa.

SLAMD is applied in multiple development cycles—ideally 6 to 8—with each cycle lasting approximately 28 days.

During the SLAMD demo, we have tested in total of 32 recipes, divided into 6 cycles of optimization with SLAMD, each cycles includes 4 recipes (8 recipes for the first two cycles) to obtain data of compressive strength at 28 days in physical concrete lab. Each data point was based on the average value of at least 3 samples.

The expected "success" was to be able to demonstrate SLAMD as a digital lab is able to predict compressive strength with tested binder materials, in order to shorten the experimental time for developing new recipes.

Image 1: Lab results of compressive strength of mortar recipes generated by SLAMD (All cycles)

FEASIBILITY HYPOTHESIS

SLAMD should be able to predict feasible mortar formulations with $\geq 30\%$ cement substitution using recycled inputs (glass and concrete fines) that achieve $fc_{28d} \geq 30$ MPa. We randomly chose 8 recipes within the test space for cycle 1 to build up our database. In the later cycles, SLAMD would be able to optimize the recipes and predict the compressive strength.

Validation: in Cycle 1, We have one recipe reached over 30MPa and one recipe reached 29MPa, which means the target is technically feasible.

OPTIMIZATION HYPOTHESIS

Iterative SLAMD cycles (6–8 total) will improve formulation quality over time by increasing the number of valid mixes that meet the target ($fc_{28d} \geq 30$ MPa) and by narrowing the range of compressive strength outcomes — i.e., reducing performance variability between formulations.

Validation: Improvement will be evaluated by analyzing how compressive strength (fc_{28d}) evolves across SLAMD cycles, focusing on trends in average values, minimum values, and the spread (standard deviation) of results within each cycle.

PARAMETER INFLUENCE OBSERVATION

Based on the variation between lab data and SLAMD prediction, there are other factors that influence the compressive strength but were not monitored in the SLAMD system yet, maybe those factors effecting the reactivity of new binders, such as chemical compositions and particle size.

EXPLORE-EXPLOIT STRATEGY HYPOTHESIS

Use of SLAMD’s explore mode in early cycles and exploit mode in later cycles enhances the balance between discovering novel formulations and optimizing known high performers.

Validation: Effectiveness of this strategy will be assessed by analyzing the diversity of proposed formulations and the progression in success rates across SLAMD cycles.[2.1][2.2] In the last cycle of optimization (cycle 6), the deviation between lab result and predicted result has been reduced to 8%, instead of 22% in cycle 5.

IMPACTS AND REPLICATION

CATEGORY	IMPACTS	FOCUS	CONTRIBUTION LEVEL
Scientific	I1-I6	Knowledge creation, CP-IM data models, predictive methods	High
Societal	I7-I12	Training, awareness, stakeholder engagement	Medium-High
Techno-economic	I13-I18	New value chains, digital tools, replication potential	Medium-Low

REPLICATION POTENTIAL

The SLAMD-tool can be scaled and replicated across different production sites and material streams, as long as sufficient material data and process parameters are available. Its transferability is high because the underlying models can be retrained or fine-tuned to local alternative binders, mix designs, and performance requirements. Successful replication depends on access to reliable input data (chemical composition, particle size, reactivity), local regulatory frameworks governing the use of alternative binders, and the availability of technical expertise to validate and adjust the generated recipes. With these conditions in place, the tool can be deployed to support recipe development in diverse industrial environments.

CONTACTS

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TECHNICAL HIGHLIGHTS

Basic screening/control of the specification of raw materials which could influence the performance of the binder, such as particle size distribution, fineness, chemical composition.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

KPI 1

Baseline

$f_{c28d} \geq 30$ MPa

Expected / Achieved

50% / 25%

KPI 2

Baseline

Substitution level ≥ 30 %

Expected / Achieved

This KPI is mostly met, because almost all designs have $RGP+CF \geq 30\%$.

KPI 3

Baseline

Ability to predict strength (predicted f_{c28d} , values against laboratory measurements)

Expected / Achieved

Overall, KPI 3 is partially achieved. The workflow demonstrates a clear improvement in predictive capability over successive cycles and achieves better-than-baseline accuracy by Cycle 6. However, the predictive trajectory is not monotonic, largely due to laboratory inconsistencies and material variations in early and mid-cycles, as well as targeted exploration of high-substitution regions where no prior labeled data existed.

LINKS

<https://slamd-demo.herokuapp.com/>